

Last chance saloon for EU Cohesion Policy post 2027

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AEIDL Senior Expert on Territorial Development sums up key challenging ideas for the next generation of EU Cohesion Policy

This time is really different

Each time the EU budget cycle starts gearing up there is a [concern](#) from within DG REGIO and the policy community around EU Cohesion that this time might be the last blow to a policy that amounts to 1/3 of the EU Budget (€392bn). Depending how you count, the EU Structural and Investment Funds are either the first or the second largest EU heading (together with the Common Agricultural Policy, which includes the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development or EAFRD, also a Structural Fund). Cohesion Policy is geared towards achieving the EU goal of Economic and Social and Territorial Cohesion set out in the Lisbon Treaty.

It is, however, a policy that feels constantly under threat. Back in 2003 we had the [Sapir Report](#) which, according to some, advocated the transfer of Cohesion funding – presently under shared management by Member States, Regions and local authorities – to thematic funds (research, transport) centrally managed at EU level. We had also in the early 2000s the “Lisbonisation” of Cohesion policy, as a response to the critique that beyond large infrastructural investments it was not effective enough in delivering economic competitiveness. The move of CP towards [financial engineering](#) (JESSICA, JASPERS, JEREMIE loan funding) was a [move](#) to address this. It was, however, judged as insufficient, hence the creation of EFSI, aka the “Junker fund”. Cohesion Policy is also a classic example of mission creep as Cohesion was increasingly expected to not only reduce territorial disparities (as mandated by art. 174 TFEU) but

also to become the main vehicle to deliver wider EU objectives such as Barroso’s Europe 2020 strategy and more recently Von der Leyen’s EU Green Deal. The policy risks coming apart at the seams.

On top of its ever-expanding remit, it has been the main EU instrument to address sudden shocks such as the 2008 financial crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, and more recently, the crisis in Ukraine, with successive omnibus packages agreed in the middle of the programming period to [simplify](#) the rules to spend faster, and avoid [significant underspends](#) even 3 years after the official end of the 7 year budget period. Part of this pressure is paradoxically the result of the success of Cohesion Policy in mobilising the (net contributing) Member States – for which Cohesion funding is just about the sole source of public investment – and its very active territorial constituency (transition regions, peripheral regions, cities, etc.) to the point that most EU policies (and Commission Directorates-General) essentially rely on Cohesion funding to deliver their own priorities, as their own programmes are comparatively much smaller.

We had also notable shifts within the structure of the policy, which in the 2014-2020 period saw a move towards consistency across the various Structural Funds by way of tying all of them together by an EU-wide Common Strategic Framework of 11 Thematic Objectives, a national Partnership Agreement, and at local level by the option of using integrated territorial development instruments such as Community Led

Local Development (CLLD) and Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI). 2014-2020 also included CAP's Pillar II, aka, EAFRD, within its structure. This architecture was dismantled in 2021-2027, with EAFRD in particular moving entirely outside the Cohesion Policy's legal framework and programmed separately in each Member State through a CAP Strategic Plan sitting separately from the Cohesion Partnership Agreements. Within the outstanding Cohesion funds, the European Social Fund has traditionally been sitting somewhat uneasily within Cohesion policy; there was even an attempt back in 2017 to move it completely outside Cohesion policy and refashion it as a [Human Capital fund](#). In the end, the ESF+ remained part of Cohesion policy but quite pointedly it was placed under a separate heading of the 2021-2027 budget.

This time it is different. COVID-19 happened in 2020. This means that for the first time massive common EU debt issuance was agreed in the form of Next Generation EU. Its main component, the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) [doubles the size](#) of Cohesion Policy while it will finance almost the same activities as the Regional, Social and Cohesion funds (RRF is also legally grounded in 174 TFEU). The crucial difference is that RRF is directly managed at EU level, though in practice its management is centralised at national level without any explicit territorial dimension. Crucially, MRR payments are provided in advance and upon meeting successive milestones, often not linked to the costs incurred (Finance Not Linked to Costs, or FNLC). This promises to be a much faster procedure than the Cohesion method of reimbursing Managing Authorities for only part of the costs incurred by them, often quite some years earlier - and only after a painstaking process of verification of all paperwork, reporting and audit.

One or many Cohesion policies?

It was never properly explained why EAFRD and the rest of Cohesion Policy went their separate ways – with the exception of the very loose possibility of having a so-called [lead fund](#) approach. It does not seem to serve any public good that two policies aimed at delivering Territorial Cohesion in rural areas are programmed and delivered separately. This, if anything, will reinforce the silo tendencies at domestic level. Common sense suggests that at the very least all EU funds financing investments are designed, programmed and delivered in an integrated fashion, at the very least by a European Partnership Pact/ Common Strategic Framework that is then replicated at national and, where applicable, at regional and local levels.

A more radical approach, which has been hinted in recent months, is to split the present farm and non-farm elements of EAFRD and link or transfer the former to Cohesion policy as in 2014-2020. The iron law of bureaucratic maximisation suggests that this scenario is far reaching and therefore unlikely. There might be EU bubble reasons (aka epistemic or policy communities), then replicated

The European Court of Auditors has identified serious deficiencies in the FNLC methodology and the absorption of RRF funds is significantly lower than what is necessary to spend it all by end of 2026, four years before the present Cohesion programmes for ordinary EU Budget 2021-2027 need to be fully finalised.

Still, with RRF a very large Rubicon has been crossed. The 2028-2034 budget will not be a return to the pre-2020 status quo. The most evident proof of this is the new [EU Social Climate Fund](#) with no less than €72bn financed by the new EU "own resources" (emissions trading, etc.), and following the RRF template, including centralised management. To be launched in 2026, this large already budgeted amount will shape the post 2027 EU Budget negotiations well before they actually start. So, like it or not, times are a-changin' for Cohesion policy.

As the new EU budget and the Cohesion policy proposals are due as early as Spring 2025, beginning almost three years of legislative and programme negotiations, discussions are presently in full gear as evidence in the [High Level Group](#) report, the [9th Cohesion Report](#), as well as the [CoR](#) (Boc- Cordeiro), [EESC](#), European Parliament [Novakov](#) REGI and [Carvalhais](#) AGRI Reports, [Cohesion Alliance](#) and plenty of contributions such as [EPC](#), [Spatial Foresight](#), [EPRC](#), [CEPS](#), [CPMR](#), [CEMR](#), [ELARD](#) and indeed the recent [Regional Studies Association](#) CPnet book to which this author contributed, to say a few.

AEIDL has also provided an [outline position for the new EU term](#). We have also modelled the strategic EU policy options of our [MOVING](#) Horizon project. This piece will not try to take stock of all this but build from this, proposing some hopefully provocative ideas to move the debate forward.

domestically, on why different funds to fund the same things exist at all. However, the end beneficiaries need not to be concerned by this EU programme complexity. EU Fund consolidation or synergic interaction of programming and delivery needs to be designed from the point of view of the final beneficiary/final delivery agent, rather than as at present these being the knock-on effect of decisions stemming from the upper branches of the EU multilevel governance tree.

'The stakes for the European Union are now higher than ever. If it is to survive and thrive, it needs well-functioning policies. Few policies can contribute as much to the European project as the Cohesion Policy. But it needs to work well to help deliver a more efficient, cohesive, and resilient Europe. This edited volume by Dotti, Musiałkowska, De Gregorio Hurtado, and Walczyk provides a welcome and timely multidisciplinary reflection about how to improve the policy and help the EU brave the many challenges it currently faces.'

– Andrés Rodríguez-Pose, London School of Economics, UK

Source: Elgar Publishing

Bonfire of EU instruments?

There has been a [proliferation](#) of EU policy and delivery instruments, particularly on local development. There are no less than 12 instruments relating to urban policy alone, with a similar number for local sustainability initiatives. While there are chronological reasons for this to happen. For instance: a new Commission identified a new priority that it felt that it was not properly served by the existing EU toolbox. Such was the case of the Just Transition Fund, the Long Terms vision for rural areas, or previously the Youth Employment Initiative.

Still, the end result is a higher level of complexity and a further disconnect between EU initiatives. For instance: capacity-building initiatives such as the Cities Missions or the EU Covenant of Mayors are not linked with EU Cohesion funding. The emerging result is a multiplicity of instruments that even EU specialists fail to fully grasp, let alone the final beneficiary. The recent [EU rural toolkit](#) is more the expression of a problem than a solution to this complexity.

There is an emerging consensus (recent EU budget conference, some reading of the 9th Cohesion report) that some rationalisation may be coming. In this case the failed attempt back in 2018 with the [proposed EU Urban Initiative](#) is a cautionary tale about how hard this will be. Still, there might be fewer but more multi-purpose instruments with bigger financial allocations and more adaptability. That said, there might be reasons that fewer is not better (very specialised or experimental policy issue, very specific set of eligible beneficiaries or territories, for instance). Better Regulation principles need to be more effectively applied so that there is a proper methodology to decide if it is better to create a new instrument or simply expand the remit or funding of existing ones. That is the purpose of the new [Maupertuis CoR Opinion](#), which this author is contributing to.

Source: 9th Cohesion Report

The end of Cohesion as the emergency wallet of the EU budget?

Cohesion policy has increasingly been the first respondent where a major unexpected crisis has arisen: the Omnibus package after the 2008 crisis, [CRI](#), [CRII+](#), [CARE](#), [STEP](#) packages against the pandemic have always drawn on the repurposing of EU Cohesion resources as the key if not the only substantive financial lever to address successive [polycrises](#). Paradoxically, the COVID-19 is not only a threat to CP as we know it but also an opportunity to free Cohesion from the need to be urgently tweaked each time

a crisis emerges. As the Gordian knot of common EU debt issuance has been breached with Next Generation EU, and furthermore with the Social EU Climate Fund deal and STEP, then it should be logical that the 2028-2034 budget recentres Cohesion Policy in its mission as defined in the Treaties while the emergency funding for the next shock is drawn common debt issuance mechanisms or by the new "Own resources".

No Cohesion without the Right to Stay?

There's no Cohesion possible in Europe without the Right to Stay. Despite the 1 trillion (1000 billion) of EU investment since 2000 and the undoubtable progress of those regions further away from the EU average, the fact is that EU convergence happens in hiccups. The implicit tendencies of the EU Single Market are towards scale and, if anything, further reinforcement of the [Blue Banana](#) that historically been the backbone of Western Europe plus the national capitals – to the detriment of anywhere else. The critique on [depopulation/demographic challenge](#) (Spain, Portugal, Italy but with limited echo at EU level), [Brain Drain](#) (Eastern Europe, has had some [success](#) in making its case at EU level) and the more recent concept of [Development Trap](#) hint that EU policies and in particular Cohesion are not enough to counter the centripetal tendencies of the Single Market towards size and metropolisation. This is why the contribution of Enrico [Letta](#) for the European Council is a timely one, for it marries a stronger and scalable Single Market with a reinforcement of Cohesion and other instruments such as State Aid, guaranteed basic services (as we proposed in our previous [Opinion on Art. 174 TFEU](#)) a timid allusion of the “buy local” clauses in procurement.

Quite clearly, while Letta's paper is a proportionate response to the protectionist measures in USA and China, the Letta Report rightly notes that this should not be an alibi for endorsing cronyism in handing public subsidies. All this would point for an expanded role and more capacities of the functions presently held by DG GROW.

Left: Total population change by NUTS 3, 2010-2021/ Right: Average population change per decade by area of 5x5km, 1961-2021
Source: 9th Cohesion Report

No Cohesion without capacity and structural reforms?

Capacity building has been part of the Cohesion arsenal for quite a while already. It is estimated that “above a threshold of cohesion expenditure – calculated [at more than €120 of cohesion expenditure per capita per year](#) – government quality improvements are a far more important and realistic option for regional development than additional public investment.” For that reason, there has been an increased number of initiatives (REGIO Administrative Capacity unit, and specific support for [Lagging Regions Initiative](#), [REGIO Peer2Peer](#), etc.) and in the 2014-2020 even a dedicated [Thematic Objective 11](#) for this very issue across all Structural Funds.

At the same time, there was a concerted move outside Cohesion Policy to create a separate instrument, [the Structural Reform Support Programme](#) which started with €142.8 million and thanks to the December 2017 Economic and Monetary Union review grew to €300m; its successor the [Reform Support Programme](#) (RSP) was meant to reach €25bn in the 2021-2027 EU Budget. Then COVID happened. SRP was never approved but a significant part of its rationale was mainstreamed into RRF, and a dedicated service (DG REFORM) was created to support public authorities in reorganising their public services, even in policies well within domestic competence. At the same time, there has been a significant divide between those keen to [do reforms via Cohesion policy](#) and those who

saw the EU Semester cycle as the key tool to agree public sector and structural reforms in each Member States in their annual National Reform Programmes.

The link between the Semester and Cohesion was timidly accepted in 2019 in the so-called Annex D of the European Semester country reports where it was attempted to link each Member State Cohesion and capacity needs. In reality of course only those MS with significant Cohesion allocations can rely on them to carry out structural reforms, hence the ex-ante conditionalities or enabling conditions set as incentives by the Commission. Still, the Cohesion policy community has often been reluctant to make this link partly because in many Member States the lead ministry in charge of the Semester (Economy) is different to the one responsible for Cohesion (Finance or Public Administration).

RRF has been in this respect a multibillion euro missed opportunity to really boost capacity and reform with the bulk of investment targeted to finance activities already financed under Cohesion. Assuming that RRF will not be continued post 2027 there is merit to at very least reintroduce TO11 and make Structural reforms a binding element of the Cohesion programmes, not a condition but a dedicated funding axis of the new programmes.

Payment by results (where possible)

If it ain't broken don't fix it, but do so if it is. A central criticism of Cohesion-sceptics is the [slow pace of absorption of CP](#), particularly [in some Member States](#). Though the policy has shown its ability to move to simplified ways of spending ([Simplified Cost options in Structural Funds](#) and [FNLC](#) in ESF) there has been also some reluctance to accept using it at domestic level, out of precautionary fear of national and EU audits further down the line.

The same happened when the Commission proposed the [Joint Action Plans](#), mirroring the payment by milestones method carried out by the World Bank and others: after a decade only a couple of pilots using Cohesion funding have been attempted. The problem remains that reimbursement of costs and co-financing is a barrier for those public authorities most in need of CP investment. NGEU has pushed all these hesitations aside and made FLNC (funds provided in advance and upon meeting of milestones, often not linked at all with the investment made) the rule.

There has been quite some speculation about [generalising the FNLC method in Cohesion Policy](#). The European Court of Auditors provided in this respect [a cautionary tale](#) about over-relying on FLNTC as the panacea. Hence, post 2027 could move to a more hybrid system whereby payment by milestone can make sense when investments are tangible and progress measurable (e.g. building a road), and keep the status quo where investment [cannot be sufficiently linked to outputs](#), let alone to societal outcomes (i.e. when for instance a Cohesion investment cannot be to a % increase in employment or digital literacy).

A new Local development framework

Last but not least, all these transformations have a direct effect on the EU policy landscape for local development. This is not only about eventually reducing and consolidating instruments and programmes but also [realigning non-farm EAFRD with the rest of Cohesion policy](#). The Commission calculates that [8% of EAFRD \(€24.6bn\)](#) is spent on issues beyond farming (national co-financing & top-ups included), and 8% of ERDF is compulsorily earmarked in [Sustainable Urban Development](#) – circa €30bn – plus an [estimated €45.6bn of Cohesion policy for rural areas](#).

So, an obvious starting point for 2027 is to put forward a horizontal 8% local development earmark across ESIF including the new EAFRD as the baseline. That said, the 2022 Court of Auditors report on LEADER is a key warning that repeats the same concerns [expressed in 2010](#). While there has been a [rallying](#) within the policy community to highlight the [added value](#) of LEADER, the most effective way to do this is to address these criticisms head on. This [can be done](#) by reducing investment in infrastructure, reducing the share of funding dedicated to administration, boosting transfers to non-investment beyond infrastructure such as rural entrepreneurship.

Furthermore, just as the wider Cohesion policy can steal the clothes of RRF post 2027 by adopting its allegedly faster, less bureaucratic ways of spending, local development approaches can do the same. The average size of a Horizon project on rural development is about €5 million, the same as the average CLLD/LEADER Local Action Group, yet the Horizon financial management rules are far less cumbersome than that of CP. As both are compliant with the EU Financial Regulation that sets out what is legally admissible across all the EU budget, why not simply adopt the Horizon financial rules for small-scale interventions such as CLLD- LEADER? No need to reinvent the wheel when there is one available that works already.

Conclusion

Admittedly these proposals, written as a by the author as a contribution to debate, and not necessarily reflecting the views of AEIDL, might be seen as way off the mark by many within and outside the EU bubble. Still, times are changing. When the wind blows, it is better to harness it than pretending to hold on to what is known, in the hope that the storm thrown into EU budget in 2020 by the pandemic will eventually subside.

AEIDL will continue working on formulating post 2027 EU policy proposal based on evidence from our research projects such as [BEATLES](#), [SMART ERA](#), [FUTURAL](#), [RURACTIVE](#), [RURBANIVE](#). You can join our [European Local Innovation Forum \(ELIF\)](#) for our policy events and policy outputs. We will co-organise with the Regional Studies Association and the Joint Research Centre a [workshop on post 2027 Cohesion](#) at the EU Week of Regions and Cities on 9 October 2024.

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